

CHARACTERISTICS OF SHAKESPEARE COMEDIES

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Abstract: In this article discusses the concept of comedy in Shakespeare's plays, highlights the multifaceted nature of love and the complexity of human relationships in the "Twelfth Night".

Key words: Comedies, comic, drama, city comedies, cloistress, romances, humor, tricks, love.

Izoh: Ushbu maqolada Shekspir pyesalaridagi komediya tushunchasi muhokama qilinadi, asosan, "O'n ikkinchi kecha" asaridagi sevgining ko'p qirrali tabiati, insoniy munosabatlarning murakkabligi yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Komediylar, hajviy, drama, shahar komediyalari, monastir, romantikalar, hazil, nayranglar, sevgi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается понятие комедии в пьесах Шекспира, главным образом, освещается многогранность любви и сложность человеческих взаимоотношений в «Двенадцатой ночи».

Ключевые слова: Комедии, комическое, драма, городские комедии, монастырь, романсы, юмор, фокусы, любовь.

William Shakespeare (26 April 1564 – 23 April 1616) was an English poet and playwright, widely regarded as the greatest writer in the English language and the world's pre-eminent dramatist.

By that time England had become a powerful state, but there was not much change for the better in the life of the English people and the power of money grew stronger. Shakespeare saw these contrasts and showed them in his works.

All the writing of Shakespeare deal with love, life and death and these universal themes get beautiful touch by him. His poetry and dramas reflect that he had extraordinary knowledge of human psychology. Therefore, his characters have become memorable in the field of literature. There are a lot of comedies, one of the most popular one is "Twelfth Night". The play expanded on the musical interludes and riotous disorder expected of the occasion, with plot elements drawn from the short story "Of Apollonius and Silla" by Barnabe Rich, based on a story by Matteo Bandello.

The main message of "Twelfth Night" is that only the inner self is true. Virtually all of the characters in the play adopt disguises of one sort or another, yet they cannot suppress their true selves for very long. Beneath all the duplicity, disguises, and game-playing, there are people with real feelings, which they cannot help but express. Reductively, the theme of "Twelfth Night" is the joy and pain of love. The play was written in Shakespeare's older years and he attempts to see love for all that is both good and bad about it. This may explain why "Twelfth Night" has a subtitle, 'What You Will (the only play that has one. What you want to

take away from it, where you are in your life, or how love has treated you over the years will affect your interpretation).¹

As for the characters who experience the pain of love: there is Malvolio, who falls so madly in love with Olivia that he loses all sense of reality and is eventually becomes a lunatic, having to be physically restrained. Or Orsino, who falls so in love he likens it not to ecstasy but to disease.

A comedy first and foremost, everything turns out happily in the end and the more tender elements of love are revealed. This is actually what makes Orsino's relationship with Viola so interesting: Orsino knew her first as Cesario (and indeed, for all that one can point out how rapidly he switches his affections from Olivia to Viola, it is at the same time worth noting that their friendship had been a very close one, ² with deep ties of affection, long before he learned the truth of Viola's deception). In Cesario, he had a close and highly trusted friend, someone he knew as a person, rather than just as an object of affection. Though Shakespeare's play is infused with delightful humor, its main theme arguably is the nature of love: who has it, who wants it, who deserves it. For example, Malvolio loves Olivia, but he will never have her and his character, "an affectioned ass" does not deserve her. As for the Duke, he happily gives up the Countess to the newcomer where he learns that his "boy" is a lovely maiden who will wed him. Sir Toby marries Maria for her wit, and in the end, it is only Malvolio who is unhappy, both for himself and envious of others who have fallen in love (love that is reciprocated.) The one dominant theme underlying both the plot and subplot of Twelfth Night can be gleaned from the title of the play and more importantly the subtitle, "Twelfth Night" or "What You Will". To understand the meaning of the title and how it connects to the dominant theme, one must first understand the traditions surrounding the "Twelfth Night" holiday, otherwise called "The Feast of Epiphany". Epiphany fell on the twelfth night after Christmas day, which marked the day that the Magi, or three Wise Men brought their gifts to baby Jesus. Shakespeare's play perfectly illustrates the nature of the holiday, as well as human nature as exhibited during the holiday, which brings us to his subtitle, What You Will, meaning "take what you will". On the surface, Shakespeare's play seems to be a nice comic love story, but on a deeper level, it is a portrayal of the foolishness of human nature, especially human nature displayed on wild, lawless nights. "Twelfth Night" by William Shakespeare revolves around the theme of love and the complexities of human nature. The play showcases how characters hide behind masks and disguises but ultimately reveal their true selves, emphasizing that inner feelings and identities cannot be concealed for long. Love in the play is depicted as both joyous and painful, with characters like Malvolio and Orsino experiencing the more agonizing aspects of affection. Despite the comedic elements and happy endings typical of Shakespearean comedies, "Twelfth Night" delves into the deeper, often tumultuous, aspects of love, portraying the intricacies of human emotions and relationships. The subtitled "What You Will" hints at the multitude of interpretations and reflections on love that the play offers, leaving room for individual perspectives based on personal experiences and stages in life.

Overall, while the play concludes in a harmonious manner, it also highlights the underlying complexities and challenges that love can bring, ensuring a rich and multifaceted portrayal of

¹ William Shakespeare's Twelfth Night", published in Yearly Shakespeare – 2012 ISSN 0976-9536 10, April 2012: 53–60.

² Adapted from the Folger Library Shakespeare edition, edited by Barbara A. Mowat and Paul Werstine. © 1993 Folger Shakespeare Library.

this fundamental human emotion. Through characters like Malvolio and Orsino, Shakespeare portrays the extremes of affection, demonstrating how love can lead to both euphoria and suffering. The subtleties of human emotions and the intricate dance between reality and illusion are vividly depicted as the characters navigate their relationships and self-discoveries throughout the narrative.

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